

**MANAGEMENT OF SKIN LESIONS CAUSED BY GIARDIA LAMBLIA
(KRIMI) BY CAESALPINIA CRISTA LINN (KANTAKI KARANJ)**

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INTRODUCTION

Skin diseases are very common in India. A Majority of the population is suffering from this disease, Apart from local causes systemic infections and diseases are also the cause of skin lesions. Among them worm (Krimi) infestations are also responsible for the skin lesions. Our ancient Acharyas have also described skin lesions caused by various types of Krimis. While describing the symptomatology of worm infestations (Internal) Sushtuta has mentioned certain common symptoms i. e. fever, skin dis-colouration, pain, cardiac disease, loss of appetite, diarrhoea etc. Several types of skin lesions have been described by various types of worms i, e. (i) In Amoebiasis pigmented or non-pigmented scars, granulomatous ulceration of the skin adjoining a viscera] lesion, and granulomatus mass Simulating an epithelioma in the perianal region has been observed. (ii) In Ankylostomoses (Hookworm infection) dermatitis occurs at the site of entry, sometimes creeping i.e. reddish itchy papule has also been observed by some other Species of Ankylostoma, (iii) In Ascariasis, urticaria and other allergic manifestations often predominate.

Giardia lamblia is also a common parasite invading the gastro-intestinal tract. It has been recently recognised as pathognomonic. Previously it was considered not to be pathogenic. Regarding the gastro-intestinal tract lesion malabsorption syndrome is very common in this organism. Mainly it harbors in jejunal area, It results into atrophy of small intestinal villi leading to retarded absorption. This type of lesion of *Giardia lamblia* is common throughout the world. Alongwith or as a result of malabsorption it also produces skin lesions. The nature of these lesions are erythematous patches which may occur in any part of the body, usually the colour is pink or purple. It may be associated with itching.

The concept of secondary malabsorption caused by *Giardia lamblia* can be described as 'Krimij Grahani' This is in support of an ancient physician Maharshi Harita He has documented a 6th type of grahani which is associated with several other diseases e. g. liver disorder, spleen disorder etc. krimi has been also enumerated in the same text. Thus the fact was in their view that worm infestation may be also one of the causes of 'grahani'.

There are several drugs in Indian medicine which have been described as Krimighna. Among them Kantaki Karanj which has been described as 'Kusthaghna' as well as "Krimighna". So it was advisable to have a trial of this drug to evaluate its role in skin lesions caused by *Giardia lamblia*. With this view, the present investigation has been carried out.

Kantaki Karanj is a semi creeper of Leguminosae family. It is some what controversial drug. Three drugs are described in the Ayurvedic Nighantus by this name i.e. (i) *Pongamia glabra* (Briksha karanja); Leguminosae; (ii) *Holoptalia integrifolia* (Karanji chirbilva) and (iii) *Caesalpinia crista* (Kat Karanja / Kantaki Karanj) of Leguminosae family. The last one has been taken for the trial.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

(1) Selection of the Patients

"Five patients were selected from the outpatient's department for the trial. Only those patients have been taken for the trial who have got skin lesions along with worm infestation.

(2) Stool Examination

Microscopic examination of stool was done to confirm the presence of cyst and trophozoites of *Giardia lamblia* in stool.

(3) Serum Protein Estimation and Blood Routine Examination

routine examination and serum protein estimation was conducted for anemia and protein deficiency.

(4) Administration of drug and diet

Powder of Kantaki Karanj. It is the kernel of the seed. 2 gms, thrice daily was administered orally for 15 days.

(5) Criteria for the assessment of the result**A. Complete cure**

- i. Complete disappearance of the symptoms
- ii. Complete disappearance of the skin lesions
- iii. Stool free from *Giardia lamblia* cyst and trophozoites

B. Partial cure

- i. Complete disappearance of the symptoms
- ii. Complete disappearance of the skin lesions
- iii. Stool not free from *Giardia lamblia* cyst and trophozoites

C. Failure

- i. No improvement in the symptoms
- ii. No change in skin lesions
- iii. Presence of *Giardia lamblia* in stool.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

Table: Showing improvement in signs and symptoms before and after treatment with C. Crista in Giardiasis.

S. No.	Signs and symptoms	Initial		After Treatment			
		Present in cases	%	After 7 days		After 15 days	
				Improv-ement in cases	%	Improv-ement in cases	%
1	Intermittent diarrhea	5	100%	3	60%	5	100%
2	Loss of weight	5	100%	2	40%	3	60%
3	Flatulence	5	100%	5	100%	5	100%
4	Diminished appetite	5	100%	3	60%	5	100%
5	Skin lesions	5	100%	3	60%	5	100%

Table: Effect of drug on distribution and type of skin lesions.

S.No.	Before Treatment				After Treatment			
	Distribution	Character			After 7 days		After 15 days	
		Type	Colour	Itching	Distribution	Itching	Distribution	Itching
1	Both the palms +++++	Papules	Purple	+++++	++	+	-	-
2	Upper extremities	Papules	"	+	+	-	-	-
3	Both the palms++	Papules	"	++	-	-	-	-
4	"" +	--	Pink	+	-	-	-	-
5	"" +++++	Papules	"	++	+	+	-	-

Table: Effect on Hg% and S. Protein (Before and after treatment).

S.No.	Before Treatment		After Treatment			
	Hb Gm%	S.P. gm%	After 7 days		After 15 days	
			Hb Gm%	S.P. gm%	Hb Gm%	S.P. gm%
1	12.6	3.6	13.0	4.0	13.4	4.8
2	10.2	4.4	10.8	4.8	11.5	5.2
3	13.4	3.4	13.8	4.0	14.0	5.0
4	11.6	3.5	12.0	4.5	13.2	5.4
5	12.8	4.6	13.0	5.2	13.8	5.6

Regarding stool examination Giardia was not found (negative) in any of the patients.

Hence it is obvious from the above tables that all the patients were classical cases of Grahani caused by Giardia lamblia infestation. Serum protein and haemoglobin gm% were found to be on lower side. Skin lesion was observed in every case.

After the administration of the drug there was almost 60% improvement in every case at all the aspects, only three cases were not able to regain full weight and itching in papules was also not fully subsided. However, by the administration of the drug for another one week the improvement was almost 100% except two cases who were not able to gain their full weight.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Skin lesions associated with worm infestations were known to Ayurvedic physicians much earlier. Kantaki karanj has been described to be Krimighna as well as Kushthaghna. A small series of 5 patients suffering from secondary malabsorption caused by *Giardia lamblia* has been studied. All the patients have got classical signs and symptoms. Krimij Grahani along with skin lesion at different sites.

Kantaki Karanj was administered in the dose of 2 gm thrice daily for a period of 15 days in these cases. There was symptomatic improvement in the symptoms of Grahni, simultaneously the skin lesion subsided of course stool could not become free of the organism. A study on larger series is required to confirm these findings and few more investigations have to be done to find out the mode of action of drug.